

Determination of the γ -(i. e. Volume Fraction of Nonsolvent for Incipient Phase Separation) Values of Methylmethacrylate-Acrylonitrile Copolymers*

A. K. KASHYAP, C. RAMI REDDY and (MRS) V. KALPAGAM

Department of Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore 560012

Manuscript received 12 August 1975; revised 20 October 1975; accepted 25 November 1975

Copolymers of methylmethacrylate-acrylonitrile of four different compositions (0.289 mole fraction (m.f.) of acrylonitrile (AN) for first copolymer-MA₁, 0.415 m.f. of AN for second copolymer-MA₂; 0.566 m.f. of AN for third copolymer-MA₃ and 0.657 m.f. of AN for fourth copolymer-MA₄) were prepared by the solution polymerization method, using benzoyl peroxide (0.05 mole percent) as the initiator. The selection of solvent-nonsolvent pair for fractionation was tested critically using several pairs of solvent-nonsolvent systems. The selected solvent-nonsolvent pairs are acetonitrile (MeCN)-di-isopropylether (DIPE) for MA₁, acetone-methanol for MA₂, and MeCN-methanol for MA₃ and MA₄ respectively and the respective γ -values for these pairs are 0.363 to 0.535, 0.426 to 0.695, 0.494 to 0.635 and 0.332 to 0.511. Fractionation occurs with respect to molecular weight only as is evident from the N₂ analysis of the unfractionated and fractionated samples.

POLYDISPERSITY in molecular weight, composition and structure is manifest in a binary copolymer system^{1,2}. For vinyl type of monomers, structural polydispersity is usually considered as negligible (or, to be not so influential in the fractionation), but the polydispersity of composition is of much importance which has to be taken into account while dealing particularly with solution properties^{1,2}. According to Stockmayer *et al.*² composition polydispersity is negligibly small for azeotropic copolymers and copolymers of low percentage conversion.

Fractionation by precipitation techniques^{3,4,5} is decidedly a better method to divide the sample into different fractions with respect to molecular weight. In the case of copolymers the selected solvent-nonsolvent system influences not only the polydispersity of molecular weight but the polydispersity of composition too.

Stockmayer *et al.*² selected butanone-di-isopropylether (MEK-DIPE) as the appropriate solvent-nonsolvent respectively for styrene-methyl methacrylate (St-MMA) azeotropic copolymer system, after determining the γ -values (i. e. volume fraction of nonsolvent at incipient phase separation) of solvent nonsolvent pairs for the homopolymers. However, Kotaka *et al.*⁶ pointed out that even this system appeared to be inefficient as the mole fraction of MMA is increased in the copolymer.

Shimura⁷ fractionated styrene-acrylonitrile (St-AN) copolymers of two compositions (Co-1 as 0.38 mole fraction of AN, Co-2 as 0.62 mole fraction of AN) using two solvent nonsolvent systems i. e. chloroform-methanol and dimethyl-formamide (DMF)-methanol. Reddy *et al.*⁸ fractionated the same St-AN copolymers of three different compositions (all below 0.5 mole

fraction of AN in the copolymer), using chloroform-methanol system satisfactorily. The determination of γ -values for the copolymers of St-pMOS (*p*-methoxystyrene) were reported by Coccorulli *et al.*⁹ In this case, different solvent-nonsolvent systems were tested and MEK-ethanol was considered to be suitable. In all the above cases, copolymers (not the constituent homopolymers) were taken for the determination of γ -values and the values for complete precipitation.

This paper deals with the fractionation of methylmethacrylate-acrylonitrile (MMA-AN) copolymers of four different compositions. A copolymer of this system of 0.48 mole fraction of AN content, was fractionated by Shimura¹⁰ using acetone-methanol system, but in the present investigation, the composition of AN is varied upto 0.657 mole fraction of AN in the final copolymer. A crucial insight is thought of in selecting the solvent-nonsolvent pair to be used for the fractionation of these copolymers of four different compositions.

Experimental

Polymerization : Solution polymerization method was adopted for the preparation of the copolymers of four different compositions using benzoyl peroxide (0.05 mole per cent) as the initiator. AN content in the monomer feed was varied from 0.376 to 0.842 mole fraction and DMF was used as the solvent. Conversion of the copolymers was allowed to about 20 percent. The copolymers were precipitated into methanol, redissolved twice in DMF and precipitated from methanol and dried in vacuum at 60°. Percentage of nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method and AN content was calculated. Table 1 shows the results of the monomer feed and percentage of conversion of AN content in the final copolymer.

* This paper was presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1974 at Madurai University, Madurai.

(MMA-AN) copolymer MA₁, MA₂, MA₃ and MA₄ had 0.289, 0.415, 0.566 and 0.657 mole fractions of AN respectively. The fractions of each one of these copolymers are indicated by the last numerical digit. Thus MA_{1,1}, MA_{1,2}, MA_{1,3} represent the first three fractions of the copolymer MA₁.

Fractionation : Incipient phase separation, γ -values were determined using MEK-methanol, MEK-n-butanol, MEK-DIPE, DMF-methanol, DMF-n-butanol, DMF-DIPE, MeCN-methanol, MeCN-n-butanol, MeCN-DIPE, acetone-methanol, acetone-n-butanol and acetone-DIPE system. A range of γ -values for all the four copolymers in 0.5 percent solution is determined and tabulated (Table 2).

Solvents and nonsolvents mentioned above were purified in accordance with the standard procedure^{1,2} and freshly distilled before use.

Results and Discussion

The monomer reactivity ratios r_1 and r_2 of the MMA and AN copolymer system are 1.20 and 0.15 respectively^{1,2}. These values attribute that the formation of azeotropic copolymers is impossible, but it is possible to prepare a good number of copolymers of varied compositions. Table 1 illustrates the mole fraction of the AN content in the monomer feed and in the final copolymer.

From Table 1, it is seen that for all the four copolymers, the AN content obtained by the nitrogen analysis and that from Alfrey-Goldfinger^{1,3} equation are not identical, the values being higher in the former case. This may be due to the higher percentage of conversion of the copolymers.

molecular weight without affecting the composition polydispersity, is of utmost importance.

In MMA-AN copolymers, the determination of γ -values for the respective homopolymers, as in St-MMA copolymer², is not possible in most solvent-nonsolvent pairs except the pair containing DMF as the solvent, since AN is soluble only in DMF. But in the case of St-AN copolymers, the γ -values were determined for the copolymers by Shimura⁷ : chloroform-methanol (for lower AN content) and DMF-methanol (for higher AN content) were selected as suitable pairs for fractionation. The fractionation was effected with respect to molecular weight only, in both cases. In the case of styrene - *p* - methoxystyrene copolymers, Ceccourouill *et al.*⁹ established γ -values, as well as the values of volume fraction for the complete precipitation of the copolymers in 1% solution. In both the cases, the solvent-nonsolvent pair was selected to be appropriate for which the γ -values and the values for complete precipitation ranged between 0.35 and 0.65.

In Table 2, a number of solvents and nonsolvent pairs are given along with corresponding γ -values and the values for the complete precipitation.

The γ -values and values for the complete precipitation for the corresponding homopolymers are also given in Table 2. It is evident from the γ -values of PAN in DMF, that the nonsolvents used with DMF are not suitable at all. Hence, in all the four copolymers, DMF-nonsolvent pairs were regarded as unsuitable.

The selected solvent-nonsolvent pairs are MeCN-DIPE for MA₁, acetone-methanol for MA₂, MeCN-

TABLE 1—PREPARATION OF MMA-AN COPOLYMERS

Copolymer	Monomer content in Mixture			Initiator (g)	Polymer obtained (g)	% of conversion	Wt. % of N ₂ in copolymer ^a	Mole fraction of AN in Copolymer	
	MMA (g)	AN (g)	Mole fraction of AN in monomer feed					Found ^b	Calc. ^c
MA ₁	75.0	24.0	0.376	0.190	20.0	20.2	4.675	0.289	0.267
MA ₂	56.4	40.0	0.572	0.160	10.0	10.4	7.207	0.415	0.387
MA ₃	37.6	58.3	0.746	0.122*	21.0	21.9	10.790	0.566	0.506
MA ₄	28.2	79.8	0.842	0.326**	19.0	17.6	13.310	0.657	0.595

* Azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) as initiator

** 0.075 mole %

^a Determined by Kjeldahl's method

^b Calculated from the wt % of N₂ in copolymer by Kjeldahl's method

^c Theoretically calculated using Alfrey-Goldfinger equation.

Poly(MMA-Co-AN) system does not have azeotropic composition. In addition, the allowance to percentage of conversion is more than 10% in each case. According to Stockmayer *et al.*² the composition polydispersity can be expected in all the systems. In the fractionation of this system, selection of a proper solvent-nonsolvent pair which preferentially fractionates with respect to

methanol for MA₃ and MA₄ respectively. These systems are arbitrarily selected for the fractionation. However, an important point has to be kept in mind, that the other workers^{7,9,10} selected systems of solvent-nonsolvent pairs in such a way that the values ranged from 0.35 to 0.65. In the present case also the γ -values for all the copolymers lie in the range 0.35 to 0.65.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF VOLUME FRACTION OF NONSOLVENT FOR THE INCIPIENT PHASE SEPARATION AND COMPLETE PRECIPITATION

Concentration : 0.5% solution			Temp = 25°		
Polymer	Solvent-nonsolvent system		γ -value at incipient turbidity	γ -value at complete turbidity	
	Solvent	Nonsolvent			
PMMA	DMF	methanol	0.856	0.903	
		n-butanol	0.761	0.835	
		DIPE	0.608	0.775	
	MeCN	methanol	0.723	0.831	
		n-butanol	0.795	0.920	
		DIPE	0.597	0.741	
PAN	DMF	methanol	0.139	0.235	
		n-butanol	0.054	0.533	
		DIPE	0.089	0.166	
MA ₁	MeCN	methanol	0.723	0.793	
		DIPE*	0.363	0.535	
	Acetone	methanol	0.550	0.780	
		DIPE	0.149	0.250	
MA ₂	MeCN	methanol	0.635	0.759	
		DIPE	0.215	0.487	
	Acetone	methanol*	0.426	0.695	
		DIPE	0.141	0.250	
	MA ₃	MEK	methanol	0.070	0.660
			n-butanol	0.010	0.025
DIPE			0.002	0.011	
DMF		methanol	0.703	0.795	
		n-butanol	0.407	0.585	
		DIPE	0.354	0.482	
MeCN		methanol*	0.494	0.635	
		n-butanol	0.277	0.430	
		DIPE	0.094	0.150	
Acetone		methanol	0.337	0.426	
		n-butanol	0.089	0.156	
		DIPE	0.031	0.054	
MA ₄	DMF	methanol	0.609	0.831	
		n-butanol	0.397	0.588	
	MeCN	methanol*	0.332	0.511	
		n-butanol	0.147	0.354	
	Acetone	methanol	0.141	0.561	
		n-butanol	0.031	0.104	

* Pairs selected for fractionation.

TABLE 3—PERCENTAGE N₂ CONTENT OF THE COPOLYMERS

Co-polymer	% N ₂						
MA ₁ (U.F.)	4.675	MA ₂ (U.F.)	7.207	MA ₃ (U.F.)	10.790	MA ₄ (U.F.)	13.310
MA ₁₂₁	4.665	MA ₂₂₁	7.133	MA ₃₃	10.760	MA ₄₂₁	13.400
MA ₁₄	4.633	MA ₂₃	7.150	MA ₃₅	10.780	MA ₄₃₁	13.280
MA ₁₆	4.672	MA ₂₅	7.097	MA ₃₇	10.853	MA ₄₄	13.325

U.F-unfractionated

The selected systems were made use of for the fractional precipitation. About 8 to 10 fractions were obtained in each case. In order to ascertain whether the fractionation was effected with respect to molecular weight alone, percentage of nitrogen was determined for three fractions of each copolymer selected at random. Table 3 shows the copolymer fractions used for nitrogen determination and percentage of nitrogen in the fractions.

It is evident from these values that the fractionation takes place with respect to molecular weight only. The little difference in the % of nitrogen between the value of unfractionated and fractionated samples is within experimental limits. Hence, it is assumed that the solvent-nonsolvent systems, though they are arbitrarily selected, are well suited for the fractionation of the MMA-AN copolymers.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.K.K.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi (India), for the award of a junior research fellowship.

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